

1 **Mycbp2 and NMyC compensate for Myc suppression in HER2+ breast cancer.**

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7 Myc cooperates with the polycomb complex (PRC2) and pluripotency inducing factors in the embryonic
8 stem cell program during induction of transformation in mammals. We utilized genomic methods to
9 describe relative contributions of the Myc family to the development of breast cancer based on molecular
10 subtype. We discovered unique contributions of separate Myc family members to molecular subtypes. In
11 primary tumors from humans of the HER2+ subtype, we found robust induction of the Myc family genes
12 *Mycbp2* and *NMyc*. Tumors utilize discrete Myc family genes and gene combinations in human cancers
13 and they use Myc family genes not only for transformation but their expression in the primary tumor at
14 clinical presentation suggests their continued requirement for tumor maintenance in vivo.
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